

Flow-Driven Fusion Edge Selection for Network Integration Inspired by *Physarum polycephalum*

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Abstract: *Background:* Adaptive structural changes in biological systems have inspired a range of network optimization algorithms, particularly for problems where global reconfiguration is impractical. In network design, integrating multiple independently constructed networks requires the effective selection of fusion edges to ensure stable and efficient connectivity. *Objective:* This study examines the adaptive network formation behavior of the slime mold *Physarum polycephalum* and proposes a heuristic fusion edge selection method based on flow-driven conductivity dynamics. *Methods:* The proposed method enables localized network integration by selecting candidate fusion edges based on the characteristic transport properties that emerge within the network. *Results:* Numerical simulations on random mesh networks demonstrate that the method effectively forms fusion paths between isolated networks and accelerates flow concentration along the resulting paths, even in heterogeneous network environments. The results further indicate that appropriate control of both the selection and the number of added edges is crucial for efficient network fusion under flow-conserved dynamics. *Conclusions:* Although the proposed method does not explicitly optimize shortest path length and involves several hyperparameters, it provides a flexible framework for network fusion based on local interactions. These findings suggest that biologically inspired, flow-based heuristics offer a promising approach for integrating complex networks when global optimization is infeasible.

Keywords: Network Fusion, Edge Selection, Physarum-Inspired Optimization, Flow-Based Heuristics, Graph Networks.

I. INTRODUCTION

Network structures are widely present in various aspects of modern society, including communication networks, transportation systems, sensor networks, and social networks. These networks are often expanded or modified while in operation, making it impractical to redesign the entire structure from scratch. Consequently, optimization methods that improve performance and efficiency through partial modifications while preserving existing network structures are increasingly necessary [1-3].

Under such constraints, improvements in network performance are achieved through localized structural changes. For example, when multiple networks independently constructed and operated are interconnected, local decisions, such as which pairs of nodes to connect become the primary means of structural modification. However, determining connections solely based on distance or cost may result in load

concentration on specific paths, potentially degrading the overall transport efficiency and stability of the network. Therefore, practical optimization methods are required to ensure global efficiency and stability even when only local structural changes are feasible [4,5].

In such situations, structural modifications are spatially localized, and the global structure evolves sequentially, making direct application of global mathematical optimization techniques challenging. Instead, approaches inspired by mechanisms that autonomously generate efficient structures through local interactions are considered effective [6-8].

In nature, living organisms adapt their structures in response to environmental conditions while maintaining efficient and stable functionality. Such adaptive structural changes often demonstrate high efficiency and flexibility and can be regarded as natural optimal solutions to dynamically changing environments [9].

Accordingly, in recent years, methods that mimic such biological adaptability have been applied to network

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optimization and algorithm design [10,11]. Among these, *Physarum polycephalum* has attracted considerable attention as an organism capable of forming transport networks that achieve both efficiency and redundancy through simple local rules [12,13]. When multiple *Physarum* individuals come into contact, the networks they have independently formed merge and reorganize into a new transport structure, closely resembling the problem of interconnecting independently constructed networks [14]. These structural transformations are closely related to the distribution and variation of protoplasmic flow within the tubular networks [15,16].

In this study, inspired by the flow dynamics within *Physarum* tubes, we heuristically formulate a fusion edge selection method for interconnecting isolated networks. Furthermore, numerical simulations demonstrate that the proposed method functions effectively facilitates the integration of multiple networks.

II. MATHEMATICAL MODELING

A. Physarum Solver

The Physarum solver is a model that forms networks based on the ‘use and growth’ rule, in which the thickness of the tubes changes according to the flow rate occurring within the tubes of the slime mold. Eq. (1) represents the flow Q_{ij} occurring along the edge connecting nodes i and j .

$$Q_{ij} = D_{ij}/L_{ij} (p_i - p_j), \quad (1)$$

Here, p_i and p_j represent the pressures at nodes i and j , L_{ij} denotes the length of the edge connecting the nodes, and D_{ij} denotes the conductivity, which indicates the ease of flow between the nodes.

If the source and sink nodes are labeled as m and n , they are represented as nodes N_m and N_n , respectively. As the flow is conserved throughout the network, the total flow is denoted as Q_0 , resulting in Eq. (2).

$$\sum_i Q_{ij} = \begin{cases} -Q_0 & (j = m) \\ +Q_0 & (j = n) \\ 0 & (j \neq m, n) \end{cases}. \quad (2)$$

The time-dependent variation of conductivity D_{ij} between each pair of nodes is expressed in Eq. (3).

$$dD_{ij}/dt = |Q_{ij}|^\gamma - \alpha D_{ij}, \quad (3)$$

Here, $|Q_{ij}|^\gamma$ represents a monotonic increasing function that describes the process by which the tubes thicken as the flow $|Q_{ij}|$ increases. The constant $\gamma (> 0)$ represents the growth exponent of the tubes. Based on prior research, we set $\gamma = 4/3$ to introduce diversity [17]. The term $-\alpha D_{ij}$ describes the process by which the tubes

shrink exponentially as the conductivity D_{ij} decreases. The constant $\alpha (> 0)$ represents the rate at which the tubes decay, and for simplicity, we set $\alpha = 1$ [18].

In this study, the Physarum Solver serves as a baseline model for adaptive network formation driven by flow redistribution, with its conductivity dynamics forming the foundation for the proposed fusion edge selection mechanism.

B. Fusion Edge Selection Method

In this study, we propose a fusion edge selection method for network formation based on the existing Physarum Solver model. This method considers both the conductivity value D_{ij} and the Euclidean distance d_{ij} of each edge during path formation process to determine candidate edges for fusion. The weighted average distance \bar{d}_D based on the conductivity D_{ij} of each edge E_{ij} is defined as

$$\bar{d}_D = \sum_{(i,j) \in E} D_{ij} \cdot d_{ij} / \sum D_{ij}. \quad (4)$$

Here, the set E represents the group of edges that have already formed the network, and d_{ij} denotes the Euclidean distance between nodes i and j .

In the Physarum Solver, the conductivity D_{ij} evolves according to a use-and-growth rule, whereby edges carrying higher flows become increasingly conductive and are preferentially maintained in the network. Consequently, edges with higher conductivity correspond to transport paths that are utilized more frequently.

From a physical perspective, when Physarum tubes have comparable thickness and flow velocity, shorter distances allow faster transport and earlier interaction or fusion. Therefore, both conductivity and distance play essential roles in shaping the formation and stabilization of the transport network.

Based on this observation, the weighted average distance \bar{d}_D is introduced as a characteristic length scale of the current network, representing the typical distances of transport paths that are preferentially reinforced under the conductivity dynamics.

Next, Eq. (5) shows the score s_{uv} of a candidate edge E_{uv} . The score increases when the Euclidean distance d_{uv} of E_{uv} is close to \bar{d}_D .

$$s_{uv} = \exp\left(-\alpha(d_{uv} - \bar{d}_D)^2\right), \quad (5)$$

The score function in Eq. (5) penalizes both excessively short and long candidate edges relative to the characteristic length scale \bar{d}_D , as very short edges tend to create redundant local connections, while overly long edges may introduce inefficient detours and increase

transport cost, thereby degrading global transport efficiency and structural stability. Here, the distance difference is normalized using min-max scaling to prevent large variations in distance from dominating the score. The parameter α represents the strength of the distance bias: when α is large, even small variations in distance cause the score to decrease, and only edges close to \bar{d}_D receive high scores; conversely, when α is small, edges farther from \bar{d}_D may still receive relatively high scores. This parameter can be adjusted according to the network size and situation.

The scores obtained from Eq. (5) are normalized and converted into probabilities P_{uv} , enabling probabilistic fusion edge selection from the set of candidate edges C , excluding the existing edges.

$$P_{uv} = s_{uv} / \sum_{(k,l) \in C} s_{kl}. \quad (6)$$

In the probability distribution P_{uv} , edges without setting a threshold or selection criteria for the number of selected edges. Therefore, we describe a method that uses Shannon entropy to determine the number of additional edges to be selected from the fusion edge candidate distribution.

Eq. (7) calculates the entropy H using the obtained probability distribution P_{uv} .

$$H = - \sum_{i=1}^n P_i \log P_i, \quad (7)$$

$$r = H / \log n \quad (r \in [0,1]), \quad (8)$$

Here P_i denotes the selection probability of the candidate edge i , n the total number of candidate edges, and $\log n$ the maximum entropy. The normalized entropy r is given in Eq. (8). The entropy reflects the uncertainty of the fusion edge selection: a value of r close to 1 indicates a flat distribution with multiple comparable candidates, whereas a value close to 0 indicates a strongly biased distribution dominated by a few candidates. Accordingly, higher entropy justifies the selection of multiple fusion edges, whereas lower entropy results in fewer additions.

Using the normalized entropy r , we perform linear interpolation to scale the number of selectable edges. Eq. (9) calculates the scaled number of edge selections k .

$$k = N_{min} + (N_{max} - N_{min}) \cdot r, \quad (9)$$

Here, N_{min} represents the minimum number of edge selections, and N_{max} the maximum number of edge selections. The integer value of the edge selection number k is then determined, and the final number of selected edges $N_{selected}$ is calculated in Eq. (10).

$$N_{selected} = \min(\max(\lfloor k \rfloor, N_{min}), n). \quad (10)$$

III. MATHEMATICAL SIMULATION

In this study, numerical simulations were conducted to evaluate the proposed fusion edge selection method for merging isolated networks. Two simulation conditions were considered: Condition A, in which fusion edges were added without selection bias (i.e., all possible candidate edges excluding existing ones were considered), and Condition B, in which fusion edges were added according to the proposed method.

The simulation environment comprised two isolated networks placed within the same spatial domain, with no initial edges connecting them. Fig. 1 illustrates the network configurations used in the simulations. In Fig. 1(a), two networks with identical structures are shown, each consisting of 60 nodes and 152 edges. In Fig. 1(b), two networks with different structures are used: one network with 53 nodes and 130 edges containing the source node (red circle), and another network with 145 nodes and 391 edges containing the sink node (blue circle).

Fig. 1 Random mesh network used in the simulation. Red circle represents the source node, and blue circle represents the sink node. (a) Identical-structure mesh network environment. A node number of source is 1, sink node is 93. (b) Different-structure mesh network environment. A node number of source is 47, sink node is 64.

For each environment, simulations were performed under both Conditions A and B. The total simulation

time was set to 600 steps, and the fusion process was applied after 300 steps. Before fusion, the existing Physarum model formed a transport path connecting the source and sink nodes within each isolated network. The parameters and initial values used in the simulations are summarized in Table 1.

To quantitatively evaluate the fusion performance of the networks, we focus on transport efficiency and total cost, which are fundamental metrics in flow-based network design. Transport efficiency is assessed by the convergence speed and magnitude of the flow along the final fusion path, reflecting how rapidly and effectively the source–sink connection is established under flow-conserved dynamics. As the Physarum Solver inherently redistributes flow according to conductivity, faster convergence to a stable high-flow path indicates a more efficient fusion process.

The total cost of the fused network is evaluated based on the number of additional edges introduced during the fusion process. Excessive edge addition increases construction and maintenance costs and may dilute flow across the network, whereas insufficient edge addition may hinder the formation of a stable fusion path. Therefore, an effective fusion strategy should achieve rapid path formation with a limited number of added edges.

Collectively, these metrics provide a comprehensive evaluation of the proposed method across different network configurations and parameter settings.

In this study, flow-based metrics are adopted instead of shortest-path length because the Physarum model optimizes network structure through adaptive flow redistribution rather than explicit shortest-path computation, making transport dynamics a more appropriate indicator of fusion performance.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

From the numerical simulations, the formation of fusion paths and the time-dependent changes in flow were analyzed for each condition. Additionally, the selection characteristics of the proposed method were clarified.

A. Identical-structure Mesh Network Environment

A-1. Fusion Path Formation

Fig. 2 illustrates the process of fusion path formation in the identical-structure mesh network environment. Figs. 2(a) and 2(b) present the results for Conditions A and B, respectively, where edges carrying higher flow

are depicted as thick red lines, and edges with lower flow are shown as thin blue lines.

Before the fusion process (step = 300), only small amounts of flow were observed near the source and sink nodes, and no path connecting them was formed. After fusion was initiated, both conditions produced a path connecting the source and sink toward the final simulation steps. Immediately after fusion (step = 302), new paths appeared in both conditions, with small flows distributed across multiple edges.

At step = 410, clear differences emerged between the two conditions. Under Condition A, the flow along the final fusion path remained weaker than the flow circulating within the existing network structure. In contrast, under Condition B, the flow along the fusion path was already comparable to the internal network flow, indicating more rapid path reinforcement. Notably, the set of edges constituting the final fusion path was identical in both conditions, indicating that the difference lies in the convergence speed rather than the final topology.

A-2. Changes in Fusion Edge Selection Score and Probability in the Proposed Method

Under Condition B, the proposed fusion edge selection method assigns scores and selection probabilities based on Eq. (5), which depend on the parameter α . Fig. 3 shows the score and probability distributions for all candidate edges in the node–node matrix.

Fig. 3(a), 3(b), and 3(c) correspond to $\alpha = 5, 10,$ and $20,$ respectively. The maximum scores obtained were $0.723, 0.523,$ and $0.274,$ and the numbers of selected edges were $77, 62,$ and $45,$ respectively. When α was

Fig. 1 Fusion path formation process in identical-structure mesh networks. (a) Condition A: Addition of all combinations of edges, (b) Condition B: Addition of edges selected by the proposed method ($\alpha = 10$). The color bar on the right represents flow. The fusion process begins after $step = 300$.

small, scores and probabilities were broadly distributed, resulting in the selection of numerous edges. As α increased, the distributions became more localized, resulting in fewer selected edges.

Fig. 2 Edge selection probability and edge score for Condition B with varying parameter α in identical-structure environment. (a) $\alpha = 5$, (b) $\alpha = 10$, (c) $\alpha = 20$. The left side shows edge selection probability, and the right side shows edge score.

A-3. Changes in Flow Within the Path

As shown in Fig. 4, the final paths formed under both Conditions A and B consist of the same edges. In the existing model, the law of flow conservation holds, and according to Eq. (2), the inflow and outflow at the source and sink nodes are equal. Therefore, the total flow Q_0 can be estimated from the edges connected to the sink node and carrying flow. As shown in Figs. 1 and 2, at the final time step, the flow path connected to sink node 93 was node 94.

Fig. 4 shows the time variation of the flow Q_{94-93} occurring in edge E_{94-93} . The gray line represents Condition A, the black line represents Condition B, and the dashed lines indicate the results obtained by varying the parameter α under Condition B. Before the fusion process, the flow was identical under both conditions; however, after the fusion began, the flow exhibited different trends depending on the condition. Comparing Conditions A and B, Condition B achieved a flow close to the total flow $Q_{94-93} \cong 4.8$ for all values of α before step = 400, whereas Condition A reached a similar level only after step = 400.

Under Condition B, the flow at step = 370 was approximately $Q_{94-93} \cong 4.21, 4.54, 3.77$ for $\alpha = 5, 10$, and 20, respectively. Both cases $\alpha = 5$ (with the largest number of selected edges) and $\alpha = 20$ (with the smallest number of selected edges) exhibited slower flow concentration compared to $\alpha = 10$. This suggests that when α is small, edge selection becomes more lenient and may include unnecessary edges, whereas when α is large, the selection becomes overly restrictive and may exclude short and effective connections. These results indicate that the number of selected edges plays a crucial role in efficient.

Fig. 3 Flow variation in the final edge connected to the sink node. The gray line represents edge selection for all combinations in Condition A. The black line, red dashed line, and blue dashed line represent fusion edge selection under Condition B.

B. Different-structure Mesh Network Environment

B-1. Fusion Path Formation

Fig. 5 illustrates the process of fusion path formation in different-structure mesh network environment. As in the identical-structure case, before the fusion process was applied, a small amount of flow spread radiated outward from the source node.

As shown in Fig. 5(a), after the fusion process, no fusion path was formed when all possible candidate edges were added. Although small amounts of flow appeared on all added edges, no stable fusion path emerged even at the final simulation step. In contrast, as shown in Fig. 5(b), where edges were added using the proposed method, two fusion paths were formed at step = 410, and one of these paths persisted until the final step.

One possible reason why no fusion path was formed as shown in Fig. 5(a), is the large number of candidate edge combinations, which totaled 7,632. This number is approximately twice that of the identical-structure case shown in Fig. 2(a), which had 3,600 combinations. When combined with the existing edges, the total number of edges exceeded 8,000, resulting in an extremely small flow being distributed to each edge.

According to Eq. (1), small variations in flow and conductivity promote pressure equalization across the network. Consequently, the network failed to reinforce a specific path, and the fusion process stagnated without forming a stable fusion route.

In contrast, as shown in Fig. 5(b), the proposed method selectively added 91 edges, which enabled

sufficient flow concentration and ultimately allowed a fusion path to be formed.

B-2. Changes in Fusion Edge Selection Score and Probability in the Proposed Method

Fig. 6 shows the distributions of edge scores and selection probabilities obtained for Condition B in the different-structure mesh network environment. Figures 6(a), 6(b), and 6(c) correspond to the results for $\alpha = 5$, 10, and 20, respectively. For all values of α , the maximum score was 1.0, and the numbers of selected edges were 96, 91, and 83, respectively.

By comparing the score distributions shown in Figs. 6(a) and 6(c), the scores for node pairs with indices between 50 and 70 decreased as α increased.

These node indices correspond to nodes located near the source and sink nodes. As such node pairs theoretically form the longest candidate paths between the two networks, their scores were reduced by the distance-based bias introduced in the proposed method.

B-3. Changes in Flow Within the Path

Fig. 7 shows the time variation of the flow within edge E_{63-64} , which is connected to the sink node in the final fusion path shown in Fig. 5(b).

When all candidate edges were added, no final fusion path was formed. Although temporary fluctuations in flow occurred immediately after the fusion process, the flow gradually returned to its pre-fusion state over time.

For the proposed method, the flow evolution differed depending on the value of α during the interval from step = 300 to 400. At step = 320, the flow values for $\alpha = 5$, 10, and 20 were 3.58, 3.64, and 3.76, respectively. At step = 400, the corresponding values were 4.78, 4.79, and 4.75.

These results indicate that, at the early stage of the fusion process, the case with $\alpha = 20$ achieved faster connection to the fusion path. However, over time, the flow with $\alpha = 5$ and $\alpha = 10$, which involved a larger number of added edges, increased and eventually exceeded that of $\alpha = 20$. In addition, although the flow variation for $\alpha = 10$ was more gradual immediately after fusion compared to $\alpha = 20$, it resulted in the highest flow after step = 400.

Fig. 5 Fusion path formation process in different-structure mesh networks. (a) Condition A: Addition of all combinations of edges, (b) Condition B: Addition of edges selected by the proposed method ($\alpha = 10$).

Fig. 6 Edge selection probability and edge score for Condition B with varying parameter α in different-structure environment. (a) $\alpha = 5$, (b) $\alpha = 10$, (c) $\alpha = 20$.

These observations suggest that even when the number of added edges is limited, the efficiency of flow distribution along the fusion path depends on the usefulness and properties of the selected edges. Together with the results from the identical-structure environment,

this indicates that both appropriate edge selection and careful determination of the number of added edges are essential for rapidly reinforcing the fusion path.

Fig. 7 Flow variation in the final edge connected to the sink node in different-structure environment.

V. CONCLUSION

In this study, we propose a fusion edge selection method for connecting isolated networks under constraints that make global reconfiguration impractical. Motivated by the adaptive network formation of slime molds, the proposed method selects fusion edges based on local flow-driven dynamics, enabling network integration through localized structural operations rather than explicit global optimization.

Contrary to conventional approaches that rely on shortest-path computation or exhaustive edge addition, the proposed method heuristically exploits conductivity evolution to guide fusion edge selection. This approach

enables effective path formation even in environments with numerous potential inter-network connections, where indiscriminate edge addition would dilute the flow. By formalizing fusion behavior at the graph level, this study extends previous slime mold-inspired research, which has predominantly focused on cellular-scale simulations and provides a novel framework for macro-scale network fusion.

The numerical simulations demonstrated that appropriate control of both the selection and the number of fusion edges is critical for efficient network integration. In particular, the results showed that excessive edge addition hinders path reinforcement under flow-conserved dynamics, whereas overly restrictive selection may exclude promising connections. These findings highlight the importance of balancing exploration and concentration in local edge selection to achieve rapid fusion path formation.

Several limitations of the proposed method remain. First, it does not guarantee shortest paths, instead prioritizing transport efficiency based on flow dynamics. Second, the selection process depends on hyperparameters α in Eq. (5), and the development of automatic parameter tuning mechanisms that account for network scale and topology is an important direction for future work. In addition, the current implementation applies fusion as a static operation at a predefined time step; extending the method to a fully time-dependent fusion process may enable adaptive integration in dynamically evolving networks.

Future work will focus on applying the proposed method to practical network structures, such as transportation and urban infrastructure networks, where connectivity must be optimized incrementally while preserving existing routes. By interpreting nodes as functional locations, such as stations, stops, or public facilities, the method can support flexible prioritization reflecting spatial or societal demands. Furthermore, evaluating fusion performance using task-dependent metrics, such as robustness, redundancy, and maintainability will be essential for adapting the approach to real-world requirements, including disaster evacuation planning and resilient infrastructure design. Empirical validation using real-world datasets, such as transportation networks derived from OpenStreetMap, will provide further insight into the practical applicability of the proposed framework.

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